

EOM4SOIL WP 5.1: Synthesis report of current limitations of contaminants in external organic matter (EOM) regulated by law and of different monitoring studies of member countries

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Executive summary

The project EOM4SOIL aims, amongst others, at proposing best management practices of organic matter (OM) for soil amendment and improving soil health. Therefore, data of contaminants such as metals, organic compounds, impurities and pathogens in OM such as compost, digestate, (sewage) sludge, etc. were gathered from ten different countries (Austria, Belgium, Italy, Finland, France, Lithuania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and Turkey). The “e” of EOM defines “external” and is OM added to soil as fertilizer that did not origin from the same field as applied and/or has undergone transformations.

Authors from the different countries compiled datasets of contaminants in EOM regulated by law and monitored in their countries. All data were joint in a database distinguishing between regulated and monitored contaminants in the countries and various OM. Mean values of contaminant concentrations of monitoring studies and reports were copied into the database and transformed, where possible (for instance all concentrations needed to be $\text{mg/kg}_{\text{dry matter (dm)}}$), so that they could be analyzed and compared with regulated limit values. From all contaminants regulated, inorganic contaminants made three fourths, whereas from all monitored contaminants metals were half of all entries. In contrast, far more organic contaminants were monitored (46%) than regulated (4%). Additionally, regulated organic contaminants contained rather legacy compounds such as PAHs, PCBs or OCP whereas monitoring studies investigated PFOS, sulfonamides, parabens, phthalates, and flame retardants (for abbreviations see Table A 2). Obviously, regulation in most countries is “behind” environmental science investigating emerging contaminants.

Organic matter covered by laws and in monitoring studies were compost, digestate, (sewage) sludge, manure, biochar, and various other organic matrices not belonging in one of the aforementioned categories. Animal by-products and nitrogen (N), phosphorous (P), and potassium (K) NPK combinations in unspecific OM were only reported in regulations but not in any monitoring study or report.

Regulated and monitored means of cadmium (Cd), the sum (Σ) of the 16 polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (ΣPAH_{16}) assigned priority compounds by the US environmental protection agency, and the Σ of the polychlorinated biphenyls ($\Sigma\text{PCB}_{6, 7, 8}$) of six, seven or eight PCB congeners were compared. These contaminants monitored were, on the basis of the present data, all well below most regulated limits except for Cd in miscellaneous OM, which was only below regulated limits. This was an overall positive result. However, due to the mean (but not the extreme or single) value(s) of individual studies considered for this overall data evaluation the concentrations could well spread over a wider range than reported here. Also, monitored concentrations reported by the different authors below the limit of quantification (LoQ) could not be considered as a value because $<10 \text{ mg/kg}_{\text{dm}}$ is not a number. Therefore, distributions of monitored concentrations could also well be lower than the reported ones here.

Overall, from the available data, chemical contamination of EOM was mainly below corresponding regulated concentration values and its application in the respective context therefore not limited. However, the current data proofed to be limited (e.g. in terms of countries), hard to retrieve (e.g. often only published in grey literature not reporting for instance on LoQ, number of replicates, etc.), heterogeneous (e.g. in terms of congeners/representative compounds assessed, analytical methodologies), partly inappropriate (reported concentrations other than mg/kg_{dm} such as g/ha , g/ha in 1, 2 or 10 years, $\text{mg/kg}_{\text{P}_{205}}$, $\%_{\text{fresh weight}}$, $\text{ng TE/kg}_{\text{dm}}$, etc., could not be included here,) and scattered (e.g. in terms of EOM categories, analytes covered).

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1 Introduction

The project “External organic matters for climate mitigation and soil health”, EOM4SOIL, aims at proposing best management practices of external organic matter (EOM), pre-processing and application on soil to contribute to climate change mitigation and improve soil health. Examples of OM are manure, slurry, compost, sewage sludge, digestate, etc. “**External**” defines the OM put on a soil as fertilizer that **does not origin from the same field as applied and/or has undergone transformation(s)** (pre-processing such as composting or anaerobic digestion, etc.).

Sources of EOM, especially urban residues such as sewage sludge, composts and digestate contain contaminants. Restrictions and quality certificates of different European member states try to avoid deleterious effects of EOM to soil health by regulating and/or postulating limits of contaminants in organic fertilizers. The aim of this report is to provide an overview of contaminants (i) regulated/postulated in different EU member states and (ii) summarize reports and scientific articles about monitoring studies concerning contaminants in EOM.

In the following, the compilation of the database underlying this report is explained in chapter 2, material and methods. All contaminants, irrespective of regulated or monitored, are presented briefly in chapter 3. Chapter 4 gives an overview of regulated contaminants followed by examples of cadmium (Cd, chapter 4.1.1) where the limit or threshold values of the different countries and OM are shown. Regulated organic contaminants are described in chapter 4.2 and concentrations ranges of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) are reported in chapter 4.2.1. Chapter 5 is about monitored contaminants where the same pattern is followed as for the regulated contaminants. Chapter 6 compares regulated with monitored values and chapter 7 discusses the data and concludes.

2 Material and methods

European Joint Project (EJP) SOIL/EOM4SOIL consortium members (<https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/eom4soil>) from ten different countries (Table 1) provided data of contaminants in OM regulated in their country as well as monitored from reports published in their country and/or scientific articles. These data in different excel files were merged by the author of this report in one excel file with a sheet for regulated and one for monitored contaminants in EOM.

Table 1: EOM4SOIL consortium members who provided the data this report is based on.

Name	Country	e-mail
Gerhard Soja	Austria	gerhard.soja@ait.ac.at
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To allow for smooth data handling, thus, to search for certain names, sort, compare data, etc. an auto filter was set to the different columns in the excel database. The data sheet of regulated contaminants contained columns about the country, OM type, contaminant, unit (of the limit concentration), limit (the regulated value), and a remarks column. Monitored contaminants contained similar columns, thus, country, origin (e.g. agriculture, forestry, urban, etc.), type (e.g. compost, grass, manure, etc.) and origin specification (e.g. wood, pile I, II, ..., composted sewage sludge, 74% solid fraction of digestate (SFD) + 24% wheat straw (WS) + 2% almond shell powder (ASP), etc.) of the OM, contaminant, mean, standard deviation (sd), median, number (of replicates), unit (of concentration or observation), remark, and reference (link pointing to the report online or written as is indicated in the bibliography of scientific articles). Where entries were ambiguous or unclear authors were asked to explain. Contaminants are listed in the Annex, Table A 1 (regulated inorganic contaminants), A 2 (regulated organic contaminants), A 3 (categories of regulated contaminants), and A 4 (categories of monitored contaminants). The final database is in xlsx format and available on the EOM4SOIL webpage.

However, the different extracts of the database underlying this report needed to be “cleaned” for description and comparison. Therefore:

- Only concentrations of the same unit could be compared. This was mg/kg_{dm} because it was mostly mentioned
- Where possible other units were transferred into mg/kg_{dm}
- Entries such as “<10” were not included in the figures because it is not a number
- The points mentioned above do not hold for the pie charts about each type of contaminants regulated or monitored in the different countries
- Where collaborators indicated medians, the numbers were entered as means in this report. However, medians in the original excel database were not changed and appear in the respective column
- Entries ≠ replicates (n) because partners were instructed to indicate means (or medians) due to the fact that reports and publications show processed data and often raw data are not available. However, partners were asked to indicate the n that ranged from “not available” as high as over 2000
- Many concentration ranges are presented in boxplots where some appear in white and some are grey shaded. This has no meaning and happened because of working with different R-versions

3 Contaminants

Inorganic and organic contaminants regulated and/or monitored in Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Italy, Lithuania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and Turkey are listed in Table A 1 and Table A 2, respectively in the Annex. The tables also contain abbreviations of the contaminants. Metals are listed in Table A 1 and main categories of organic contaminants are perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs), aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), pharmaceuticals and biocides, polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs), phthalates, phenols, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), parabens, alkylbenzene sulfonates, polychlorinated dibenzo-*p*-dioxins/-furans (PCDD/F),

sulphonamides, paraffins, organochlorine pesticides (OCP), halogens, and biuret (Table A 2). Furthermore, regulated and sometimes monitored impurities and pathogens are listed in Table A 3.

4 Regulated contaminants and major EOM categories

Of the total 2862 contaminant entries regulated in 10 countries the majority, namely 2163 entries concerned metals (76%), 111 organic contaminants (4%), 122 impurities (4%) and 466 pathogens (16%, Figure 1).

Figure 1: Of the 2862 entries regulating contaminants in organic matter in ten different countries four categories were formed. Over three quarters of all entries in the database concerned metal, 16% pathogens, and 4% organic contaminants and impurities, each. Category items are listed in Table A 3 of the Annex.

From all OM regulated (Figure 2) more than 40% entered the database as organic or organo-mineral nitrogen (N), potassium (K) and phosphorous (P) fertilizer or combinations of it (NPK combinations, Table 2). All countries except Sweden and France used these categories originating from the EU regulation 2019/1009 to characterize OM that was not processed, thus neither composted nor digestated, nor was sludge, biochar or manure. Compost is the mostly put distinct and processed OM of all organic material. In spite of the NPK combination group, the miscellaneous category was >10%. Here, countries regulated national and/or specific OM as for instance Finland, Spain and Italy peat and combinations of it, Belgium woody OM in the paper industry, Finland and Lithuania growing media, Spain olive pomace paste, humic acids and seaweed extracts, and Turkey vinasse.

Figure 2: Almost a fifth of all organic material regulating contaminants was compost, 10% were animal by-products (ABP) without manure and about 40% concerned nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium (NPK) combinations of fertilizers that is described in Table 2. Miscellaneous was material NOT containing “ABP”, “compost”, “digestate”, “manure”, “NPK”, or “sludge” in the column OM type of the database and was material such as growing media, different peats, mixed topsoil, stillage, desiccated olive pomace paste, etc.

The question is whether the contaminants categorized in Figure 1 are found equal frequently in all matrices of Figure 2. Indeed, the fraction of metals regulated was the highest in all matrices and fluctuated little, between 65 and 80% (Figure 3). While organic contaminants incl. PAHs and PCBs are regulated in a few percent in compost, digestate, and sludge and even in the permil range in the NPK combinations and the miscellaneous group (Figure 2), they are not at all regulated in manure and animal by-products (ABP). In contrast, organic contaminants are well regulated in biochar but pathogens and impurities are omitted due to obvious reasons.

Table 2: Unspecific, organic material that is regulated in some countries as nitrogen, phosphorous, and potassium (NPK) fertilizer.

Material	State of aggregation	Organic origins	Class	Minerals	Fertilizer combinations
Organic	Solid	Plant	A	Peat	N
Organo-mineral	Liquid	Animal	B	Leonardite	NP
		Lignite	C		NK
					PK
					NPK

Figure 3: Fractions of contaminants regulated in different organic material (OM). Metals are listed in the Annex, Table A 1, organic compounds in Table A 2 incl. abbreviations, and impurities and pathogens in Table A 3. Contents of the miscellaneous OM is explained in Figure 2, nitrogen (N), phosphorous (P) and potassium (K) containing matrices entered the NPK combinations group and animal by-products (ABP) the respective category.

4.1 Metals

As mentioned above, the majority of contaminants regulated were (heavy or trace) metals. Figure 4 shows the percentage of the individual metals of the 2163 entries. Cobalt, Cs, ¹³⁷Cs, Cr VI, Se, Tl, and V are summarized in the miscellaneous group. Lead was most times regulated (312 times) in all countries followed by Cd, Cr, Cu, Hg, Ni, and Zn. Cadmium was chosen as representative heavy metal example for further analysis concerning regulated limits in OM in this report. All other metals are presented in the original excel database.

Figure 4: Of the 2163 entries regulating inorganic contaminants in organic matter the percentages of the eight most mentioned metals are shown in a pie chart. The miscellaneous group contains Co, Cs, ¹³⁷Cs, Cr VI, Se, Tl, and V.

4.1.1 Cadmium (Cd)

Of the 2163 metal entries in OM 279 concerned Cd and of these 246 entries had limit values in form of mg/kg_{dm}. Cadmium in all OM types regulated in the 10 countries ranged from the minimum of 0.5 mg/kg_{dm}, over the 1st quartile of 1.2, to the median of 2.0, mean of 2.4, 3rd quartile of 3.0 to the maximum of 40 mg/kg_{dm} (Figure 5A, B). The outlier limit at 40 mg/kg_{dm} was for sewage sludge in Spain if soil pH is >7 and the one at 20 mg/kg_{dm} if pH is <7. A sewage sludge with 10 mg/kg_{dm} in Belgium can be used in agriculture depending on the type of process. In Figure 5B the y-axis was cut at 6 mg/kg_{dm} for a better overview.

Regulated limits in 10 countries

Regulated limits in 10 countries

Figure 5: Regulated limit values of cadmium (Cd) in all organic material (OM) of 10 countries (A). Panel B cuts the y-axis at 6 mg/kg_{dm} for a better overview.

In the following, the OM categories from Figure 2 are shown below in boxplots (except biochar due to the small entry number). Regulated limit values of Cd in compost (Figure 6A, 39 entries) ranged from 0.7 to 3.0 mg/kg_{dm} where the median and the 3rd quartile fell together at a concentration of 2.0 mg/kg_{dm}. Digestate were only regulated in eight entries of Austria, Belgium, France and Italy. Often, Cd in digestate was regulated by g_{Cd}/ha in one, two or ten years that could not be compared with the common mg/kg_{dm}. Digestate regulated (Figure 6B) ranged from 0.7 to 6.0 mg/kg_{dm} (min, max), having a median of 1.5 and a 3rd quartile at 1.9 mg/kg_{dm}. The maximum at 6.0 mg/kg_{dm} was from Belgium for household waste.

Figure 6: Regulated limit values of cadmium (Cd) in compost (A) and digestate (B)

Regulated limit values of Cd in sewage sludge (Figure 7A, 12 entries) ranged from 0.5 to 40 mg/kg_{dm} (min, max) where the 1st quartile was 2.0, the median 4.5 and the 3rd quartile 10 mg/kg_{dm}. The limit of 40 mg/kg_{dm} in sludge was set by Spain if soil pH is >7 and the one of 20 mg/kg_{dm} if soil pH is <7. Regulated limit values of Cd in manure (Figure 7B, 21 entries) ranged from 0.7 to 3.0 mg/kg_{dm} (min, max), where the latter fell together with the 3rd quartile and the median was at 2.0 mg/kg_{dm}.

Figure 7: Regulated limit values of cadmium (Cd) in sewage sludge (A) and manure (B).

The Cd content in biochars was only regulated by Austria and Italy. Austria differentiated the limit according to the use of biochar, which is declared in the European Biochar Certificate (EBC, 2012-2022). Italy just indicated the process, pyrolysis or gasification, for the limit value. Consequently, this category only has four entries, with a minimum of 0.7 mg/kg_{dm} for biochar in organic agriculture according to EBC and a mean, median and maximum value of 1.5 mg/kg_{dm} for agricultural and urban use (EBC). Italy regulated Cd in biochar by one value, 1.5 mg/kg_{dm}, for organic soil improver for sale.

Figure 8 depicts the range of miscellaneous OM (Figure 2) inputs (56 entries, panel A) and ABP (23 entries, panel B). Both categories exhibited almost the same and narrow ranges from 0.7 to 3.0 mg/kg_{dm} with a median of 1.5 mg/kg_{dm} that fell together with the 1st quartile for the miscellaneous OM and of 2.0 mg/kg_{dm} for ABP.

Figure 8: Regulated limit values of cadmium (Cd) in miscellaneous organic matter (OM, A) and in animal by-products (ABP, B).

The rest of the entries (123) of OM belonged to NPK combinations with the properties listed in Table 2. Spain took most of the categorisation over from the EU regulation 2019/1009. This not only holds for Cd but also for Cr, Hg, Ni, Pb, Cu, and Zn. The range was the same or very similar as for miscellaneous OM and APB with 0.7 to 40 mg/kg_{dm} (min, max), median of 2.0 and a 3rd quartile of 3.0 mg/kg_{dm} (Figure 9). The outlier of 40 mg/kg_{dm} in Figure 9A was put by Lithuania for organo-mineral fertilizer if total P content was >5% of P₂O₅-equivalent by mass. Please note that the total number of compost, digestate, (sewage) sludge, manure, biochar, miscellaneous OM, NPK combinations, and ABP was >246 entries. This was due to counting twice NPK combinations that were for instance “N-fertilizer of animal and plant origin”. Once it entered ABP and once NPK combinations.

Figure 9: Regulated limit values of cadmium (Cd) in nitrogen (N), phosphorous (P) and potassium (K) combinations of organic matter with outlier (A) and zoomed in for a better overview (B).

4.2 Organic contaminants

Of the 2862 entries of contaminants regulated in ten countries 111 entries concerned organic compounds (Table A 2) from seven countries. This picture is not complete, as the database relies on contributions from individual countries, and not all countries provided information on organic contaminants regulated in their country. Of regulated organic contaminants almost 40% concerned PAHs, 16% PCBs or hydrocarbon indices, each, 10% dioxins (PCDD/F), and the rest (halogens, BTEX, biuret, PBDE-209, PFOS, antibiotics, mineral oil hydrocarbons, PFT, and OCP (for abbreviations see Table A 2)) was put in a miscellaneous group (Figure 10). For further considerations, the focus fell on PAHs and PCBs as these were the biggest groups and were regulated by most countries.

Figure 10: Of the 111 entries regulating contaminants in organic matter five categories could be formed. Halogens, BTEX, biuret, PBDE-209, PFOS, antibiotics, mineral oil hydrocarbons, PFT, and OCP were put in the miscellaneous group. Abbreviations are explained in Table A 2 of the Annex.

4.2.1 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)

The Σ PAH16 (16 compounds of the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) that are listed in Table A 2) only concerned 15 and the Σ PCB6 or Σ PCB7 17 of the 111 entries, which is the reason why PAHs and PCBs were not categorized into different OM as Cd. Minimum, median, and maximum concentrations in mg/kg_{dm} were 4.0, 6.0, and 30, respectively (Figure 11A) for Σ PAH16. Belgium put 30 mg/kg_{dm} for Σ PAH16 in flows from forestry/logging and wood or paper industry and 20 mg/kg_{dm} in urban sewage sludge for agriculture. Organic matter where PAHs were regulated was compost, digestate, biochar, sewage sludge and combinations of the former or of OM.

Figure 11: Regulated limit values of organic contaminants such as Σ PAH16 (A), Σ PCB6 or 7 (B, abbreviations see Table A 2) in organic matter.

Polychlorinated biphenyls are depicted as Σ PCB6 or Σ PCB7, where the latter contained PCB congeners 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153, 180 and the former omitted PCB congener 118 (Table A 2). The minimum concentration was 0.06 mg/kg_{dm}, the median at 0.2 mg/kg_{dm} and the maximum at 1.0 mg/kg_{dm} (Figure 11B). Austria put the maximum limit of 1.0 mg/kg_{dm} for Σ PCB6 in compost, France and Belgium at 0.8 mg/kg_{dm} for Σ PCB7 in composted sludge and urban sewage sludge for agriculture, respectively, and Belgium at 0.5 mg/kg_{dm} in the same matrix as for 0.8 mg/kg_{dm} but in Wallonia. The OM where PCBs were regulated was the same as for PAHs.

Note that the unit of Figure 11B is mg/kg_{dm} but often PCBs or PCDD/Fs or dioxins are indicated in ng I-TEQ/kg_{dm} or ng TE/kg_{dm} which is why they found no entry here. The unit is weighed according to the toxic equivalent (TE, old abbreviation is I-TEQ for International Toxic Equivalent). Only Austria and Switzerland regulated dioxins in compost digestate, sewage sludge, and biochar. Of the ten entries eight have a limit of 20 ng TE/kg_{dm}. Austria put a limit of 50 ng TE/kg_{dm} in compost and 100 ng TE/kg_{dm} in sewage sludge.

Finally, ten entries of France have the unit g/(ha*year). They put these limit values for green waste and biowaste compost, composted sludge, and digestates for some PAH compounds (FLT 6.0 g/(ha*year), BbF 4.0 g/(ha*year), BaP 2.0 g/(ha*year)) and Σ PCB7 1.2 g/(ha*year).

5 Monitored contaminants

Of the total 3327 contaminant entries monitored in eight countries (all of the above mentioned except Austria and France¹) the majority, namely 1641 entries concerned metals (50%), 1518 organic contaminants (46%), 45 impurities (1%), and 107 pathogens (3%, Figure 12). Sixteen entries

¹ Austria delivered an extensive study from 1994 – 2017 of heavy metals, pathogens and other parameters in composts, biowaste, sewage sludge, etc. Unfortunately, the report contained processed data mostly in form of histograms and the authors, Kompostgüteverband Österreich and the Association of Compost and Biogas Austria, did not want to reveal the raw data. However, the essence of that report in form of many different graphs can be retrieved from the persons listed in Table 1. France has, within the EOM4SOIL project, work package (WP) 1.2, its own database where monitored contaminants are listed.

concerned effects such as germination capacity, granulometry, phytotoxicity, and sprouting plant seeds, which were not considered as contaminants.

Figure 12: Of the 3311 entries concerning monitored contaminants in organic material of eight different countries half concerned metals, almost half organic contaminants, 3% pathogens, and 1% impurities. Category items are listed in Table A 4 of the Annex.

From all OM monitored for contaminants 30% entered the database as (sewage) sludge, 24% as compost, 16% as digestate, 10% as manure, 8% as biochar, and 12% were miscellaneous matrices (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Percentages of contaminant database entries (3327 in total) monitored in different external organic matter categories that were mainly (sewage) sludge, compost, digestate, manure, biochar, and the rest of material. The latter group contained for instance ashes, fall foliage, presswater, green and household waste, scum, etc.

The question is whether the contaminants categorized in Figure 12 are found equal frequently in all matrices of Figure 13. The contaminants were not equally distributed in the different matrices. Metals were monitored in 50 to 86% of all contaminants in compost, digestate, manure, and miscellaneous OM but reached only a quarter in biochar and 29% in sludge (Figure 14). In the latter OM, organic compounds other than PAHs or PCBs, thus pharmaceuticals, PFOS, dioxins, etc. made up for 54% of the investigated contaminants. In biochar, PAHs were monitored in 74% of the entries. Pathogens were only monitored in compost, digestate and manure and impurities in the former two matrices.

Figure 14: Fractions of contaminants monitored in different organic material (OM). Metals are listed in the Annex, Table A 1, organic compounds in Table A 2 incl. abbreviations, and impurities and pathogens in Table A 4. Contents of the miscellaneous OM is explained in Figure 13.

5.1 Metals

Similar to regulated metals monitored Cd, Cu, Cr, Ni, Pb and Zn contributed to 10 – 13% of all inorganic compounds (Figure 15). The miscellaneous group contained Ag, Al, B, Ba, Bi, Co, Cr III, Cr VI, Li, Sb, Se, Sn, Sr, Tl, U, V, Y.

Figure 15: Of the 1641 entries monitoring inorganic contaminants in organic material the percentages of the ten most mentioned metals are shown in a pie chart. The miscellaneous group contained Ag, Al, B, Ba, Bi, Co, Cr III, Cr VI, Li, Sb, Se, Sn, Sr, Tl, U, V, Y.

5.1.1 Cadmium (Cd)

Of the 1641 metal entries in OM 188 concerned Cd and of these 162 entries had limit values in form of mg/kg_{dm} and were therefore comparable. Cadmium in OM of all kinds monitored in seven countries ranged from the minimum of 0.003 mg/kg_{dm}, over the 1st quartile of 0.2, to the median of 0.6, mean of 1.9, 3rd quartile of 1.2 to the max of 82 mg/kg_{dm} (Figure 16A). Figure 16B shows the same graph with a cut y-axis at 10 mg/kg_{dm}.

Figure 16: Monitored cadmium (Cd) concentrations of all organic material (OM) in seven countries (Belgium, Italy, Lithuania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey) over the whole range (A) and zoomed on y-axis (B, ≤ 10 mg/kg_{dm}).

Monitored mean Cd concentrations in compost (50 entries) ranged from 0.11 to 10.0 mg/kg_{dm} (min, max (of these means and in the following not mentioned anymore)) where the median was at 0.5 and the 3rd quartile at 0.9 mg/kg_{dm} (Figure 17A). Cadmium in digestate was monitored in 32 samples and the concentration means were slightly lower than in compost. Mean concentrations ranged from 0.01 to 8.6 mg/kg_{dm} (min, max) with a median of 0.23 and a 3rd quartile at 1.0 mg/kg_{dm} (Figure 17B).

Figure 17: Monitored cadmium (Cd) concentrations in compost (A) and digestate (B).

Monitored mean Cd in sludge (33 entries) from mainly waste water treatment plants (WWTP) and industry such as food, beverage, paper or leather and fur ranged from 0.1 to 82 mg/kg_{dm} (min, max) where the median was at 1.1 and the 3rd quartile at 1.9 mg/kg_{dm} (Figure 18A). Cadmium in manure (21 entries) had about 50 times lower mean concentrations than sludge and originated mainly from husbandry animals for dairy and meat production. It ranged from 0.003 to 1.8 mg/kg_{dm} (min, max), the median was at 0.3 and the 3rd quartile at 0.5 mg/kg_{dm} (Figure 18B).

Figure 18: Monitored cadmium (Cd) concentrations in sludge (A) from food, beverage, paper and leather and fur industries as well as waste water treatment plants and manure (B).

The mean Cd contents in biochars were monitored in five samples (no figure) of which only two samples were above the limit of quantification (LoQ). The observed mean values from biochar of tree barks were 1.2 mg/kg_{dm} and the one of vine shoots 0.6 mg/kg_{dm}. The rest of the organic material where Cd was monitored was ashes, slurry, scum for sugar factories, municipal organic waste, biogas, and presswater. The 28 observations had mean Cd concentrations from 0.18 to 9.0 mg/kg_{dm} (min, max) with a median of 1.0 and a 3rd quartile of 1.9 mg/kg_{dm} (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Monitored cadmium (Cd) concentrations in miscellaneous organic material (OM) such as ashes, slurry, scum for sugar factories, municipal organic waste, biogas, and presswater.

5.2 Organic contaminants

Seven countries monitored organic contaminants (Austria and France see footnote 1) that resulted in 1518 entries.

Figure 20: Countries that monitored organic contaminants. Percentages refer to a total of 1518 entries.

Of monitored organic contaminants 31% concerned PAHs, 15% flame retardants, 11% pharmaceuticals, 10% PCBs, 11% miscellaneous material and the rest were fractions <10% (Figure

21). Similar to regulated organic contaminants PAHs made the biggest group. Therefore, PAHs and also PCBs of monitoring studies were depicted in OM categories below.

Figure 21: Of the 1518 entries monitoring organic contaminants in organic matter nine categories were formed. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons were the biggest group followed by flame retardants, pharmaceuticals, the group of miscellaneous organic contaminants and PCBs. The rest of the contaminants contributed to <10% of the entries. The miscellaneous group contained for instance BTEX, parabens, alkylbenzene sulfonates, etc. Abbreviations are explained in Table A 2 of the Annex.

Mean concentrations, thus for instance Σ PAH16 but also individual PAH compounds such as BaP, PHE, PYR, etc. or PFT and individual PFOA and PFOS, etc. (Table A 2), of all organic contaminants in OM monitored (1383 entries) spanned over 10 orders of magnitude and ranged from 1.7×10^{-7} to 4757 mg/kg_{dm} (min, max) with a median of 0.02 mg/kg_{dm}, and a 3rd quartile of 0.3 mg/kg_{dm} (Figure 22). The minimum concentration was measured of 2,3,7,8-TCDD in Swiss digestate and the maximum of mineral oils in Belgian urban sludge. As for instance dioxins are often reported in ng/kg and PCBs in μ g/kg, concentration's span is so large and was therefore logarithmized in order to gain an overview.

Figure 22: Monitored, logarithmized, organic contaminants in all organic material (OM).

5.2.1 Organic contaminants, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)

Similar to the few entries of regulated organic contaminants only 56 of the 473 entries (31% of 1518 entries, Figure 21) monitored Σ PAH16. The other 417 entries were single PAH compounds or fractions of the 16 PAHs. Hence, also in this chapter a categorization into different OM categories would be too much of a splitting. Mean concentrations ranged from 0.006 to 438 mg/kg_{dm} (min, max, (\log_{10} -2.2 mg/kg_{dm}, \log_{10} 2.6 mg/kg_{dm})) with a median of 1.7 mg/kg_{dm} (\log_{10} 0.2 mg/kg_{dm}, Figure 23A). The highest and second highest concentration were found in two biochar samples of Spain. Nineteen entries reported Σ PCB7 and Σ PCB8 (congeners 28, 52, 101, 118, 153, 180, 138, 163 by Lithuania) mean concentrations with a minimum of 0.002 mg/kg_{dm}, a maximum of 0.3 mg/kg_{dm}, and a median of 0.01 mg/kg_{dm} (Figure 23B). The two highest concentrations of 0.1 and 0.3 mg/kg_{dm} of Σ PCB7 were recorded in sewage sludge.

Figure 23: Monitored, logarithmized concentrations of Σ PAH16 in all organic material (OM, A) and of Σ PCB7 and Σ PCB8 in OM.

6 Results of monitored and regulated contaminants

From all contaminants regulated, inorganic contaminants made three fourths whereas monitored metals were half of all entries (Figure 1 and Figure 12). In contrast, far more organic contaminants were monitored (46%) than regulated (4%). The reason for this is that regulated organic contaminants were listed for instance as Σ PAH16 (Table A 3) while those monitored were often listed as single compounds (Table A 4 or rather Table A 2). Additionally, regulated organic contaminants contained rather legacy compounds such as PAHs, PCBs or OCP whereas monitoring studies investigated PFOS, sulfonamides, parabens, phthalates, and flame retardants (Table A 2). Obviously, regulation in most countries is “behind” environmental science investigating emerging contaminants.

While OM was regulated in eight different categories (Figure 2) monitored OM could only be distributed into six classes (Figure 13). No monitoring studies did consider ABP and the generic names of NPK combinations obtained specific ones when monitored.

In contrast to the fractions rather equally distributed over all matrices except biochar and ABP of the different contaminants regulated in the various OM (Figure 3), the fractions of monitored contaminants in the different matrices were not (Figure 14). Metals were monitored in the majority of compost, digestate, manure, and miscellaneous matrices, organic contaminants mostly in sludge and PAHs in biochar.

Concerning inorganic contaminants, the fractions of regulated and monitored Cd entries were very similar. Thirteen percent of all heavy metals regulated concerned Cd (Figure 4) and 11% monitored (Figure 15).

Cadmium, PAHs and PCBs depicted in the different matrices (above) are compared by means of violin plots. Box- and violinplots are very similar. The vertical rectangle in the violinplot corresponds to boxplots. The 1st and 3rd quartile are the lower and upper limit of the rectangle and the horizontal line is the median (e.g. Figure 24). The violinplot does not show any whiskers but the distribution of the data that gives the “body” of the violin. For instance, the peak of Cd monitored in compost (Figure 24A) is at the median, which is 0.5 mg/kg_{dm} (also see Figure 17) meaning that the majority of the 50 entries has about this value. Outliers or single values marked as empty dots above the whiskers of the boxplots (e.g. Figure 17) are small humps in the violinplot (e.g. at 6.4 mg/kg_{dm} and 10 mg/kg_{dm} in Figure 24A).

6.1 Monitored and regulated cadmium

Cadmium medians of all OM types monitored, thus compost, digestate, sludge, manure and miscellaneous materials, were smaller than regulated limits (Figure 24 to Figure 26). Medians, including the majority of entries, of Cd monitored in all OM types were two (miscellaneous organic material, Figure 26) to seven (manure, Figure 25B) times lower than the medians of regulated Cd.

Figure 24: Violinplots of Cadmium (Cd) in compost (A) and digestate (B) regulated and monitored.

First to 3rd quartiles of Cd monitored in (sewage) sludge (Figure 25A) and miscellaneous OM (Figure 26) overlapped with 1st and 3rd quartiles of Cd regulated. The regulated range of Cd in (sewage) sludge (Figure 25A) was also wide, in fact, it had the widest span for Cd in OM with more than two orders of magnitude.

Figure 25: Violinplots of Cadmium (Cd) in (sewage) sludge (A) and manure (B) regulated and monitored.

Cadmium contents in the rest of the OM, thus not compost, digestate, (sewage) sludge or manure, is shown in Figure 26 as miscellaneous. Please note that the y-axis was cut at 10 mg/kg_{dm} for a better overview and the value of 40 mg/kg_{dm} of Lithuania for organo-mineral fertilizer if total P content was >5% of P₂O₅-equivalent by mass was omitted (Figure 9A). In this group, the difference was smallest with a factor of two between the median monitored and regulated. Two thirds of regulated Cd belonged in this OM type (161 of 242 entries, chapter 4.1.1) but only 17% of the monitored Cd (28 of 162, chapter 5.1.1). In general, low regulated Cd concentrations belong to class A limits (Table 2) or organically managed OM, which is also true for instance for compost.

Figure 26: Violinplots of Cadmium (Cd) in miscellaneous organic material.

6.2 Monitored and regulated PAHs and PCBs

Regulated Σ PAH16 showed a narrow range in comparison to monitored (Figure 27A) and the latter spanned over four orders of magnitude. The Σ PCB6, 7, 8 monitored ranged over two orders of magnitude and the regulated values are broader than the ones of PAHs (Figure 27B). However, also the comparison of organic contaminants showed the same pattern as with Cd, namely that the majority of the monitored Σ PAH16 and Σ PCB6, 7, 8 were below the regulated limits.

Figure 27: Violinplots of PAHs (A) and PCBs (B) regulated and monitored in all organic matter (OM).

7 Discussion and conclusions

Contaminants regulated in the OM differed from the ones monitored, not so much with regard to the nature of the target analytes, but the frequency of investigation in the various matrices. In general,

organic contaminants were monitored and prevailed in matrices where environmental fate and behavior models would predict them to occur as e.g. PFAAs, pharmaceuticals, flame retardants etc. in sewage sludge or PAHs in biochar as a result of pyrolysis.

Cadmium, ΣPAH16, and ΣPCB6, 7, 8 monitored were, on the basis of the present data, all well below most regulated limits except for Cd in miscellaneous OM, which was only below regulated limits. This was an overall positive result. However, the outcome is subject to the following limitations. Firstly, monitored concentrations entered the database as means. Thirty-seven percent of the entries of monitored contaminants reported one replicate. The rest ranged from “n.a.”, not available, to 2450 replicates. This implies that the data distribution could span over a wider range (monitored contaminants in Figure 24 to Figure 27) than reported here. The same holds for the standard deviation (sd) that was put into the database but not in the report. Often, the sd was two to three times the value of the mean, which was due to the fact that the replicates were from different fields or sites. Small sd were often from analytical replicates but the quality of the former, thus “real” replicates, was higher than the latter.

Secondly, concentrations below the LoQ should not be underestimated although they could not be taken into account in this report. Values seen in raw data such as 0 mg/kg_{dm} are wrong from an analytical point of view. The concentration of an analyte is so low that it falls below the LoQ and should be reported as such, e.g. <10 mg/kg_{dm} (which some authors did) or as “not detected” (which is even different from “not determined”). Hence, if for instance Belgium reports on PAH compounds in OM that were not detected it was an important result but found no entry in this evaluation. So, the distribution of Cd, ΣPAH16, and ΣPCB6, 7, 8 monitored would span into lower concentrations than what they are now enhancing the already positive result.

In conclusion, the example contaminants of regulated and monitored Cadmium, ΣPAH16, and ΣPCB6, 7, 8 compared in this report indicated that current contamination levels might not cause a major risk for OM recipient matrices, i.e., soil considered the above-mentioned limitations. This assessment only holds for countries that delivered their data until autumn 2022 for this report.

8 Acknowledgements

Many thanks go to the authors who compiled the data of regulated and monitored contaminants in EOM in their country Table 1.

9 References

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Annex

Table A 1: Inorganic compounds regulated and monitored in Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Italy, Lithuania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and Turkey.

Element	Abbreviation	Element	Abbreviation
Aluminum	Al	Manganese	Mn
Antimony	Sb	Mercury	Hg
Arsenic	As	Molybdane	Mo
Boron	B	Nickel	Ni
Barium	Ba	Lead	Pb
Bismuth	Bi	Selenium	Se
Cadmium	Cd	Silver	Ag
Caesium	Cs, ¹³⁷ Cs	Strontium	Sr
Chrome	Cr	Thallium	Tl
Chromia	Cr III	Tin	Sn
Chrome hexavalent	Cr VI	Uranium	U
Cobalt	Co	Vanadium	V
Copper	Cu	Yttrium	Y
Lithium	Li	Zinc	Zn

The following organic compounds are restricted by law and were reported in scientific articles and reports.

Table A 2: Organic compounds regulated and monitored in Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Italy, Lithuania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and Turkey.

Class	Compound	Abbreviation
PFAAs	Perfluoroalkyl acids	
	Perfluorobutanoic acid	PFBA
	Perfluoropentanoic Acid	PFPeA
	Perfluorohexanoic acid	PFHxA
	Perfluoroheptanoic acid	PFHpA
	Perfluorooctanoic acid	PFOA
	Perfluorononanoic acid	PFNA
	Perfluorodecanoic acid	PFDA
	Perfluoroundecanoic acid	PFUnDA
	perfluorododecanoic acid	PFDoA
	Perfluorotridecanoic acid	PFTTrDA
	Perfluorotetradecanoic acid	PFTeDA
	Perfluorohexadecanoic acid	PFHxDA
	Perfluorooctadecanoic acid	PFODA
	Perfluorobutanesulfonic acid	PFBS
	Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid	PFHxS
	Perfluoroheptanesulfonic acid	PFHpS
	Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid	PFOS
	Perfluorodecane sulfonic acid	PFDS
PFOA + PFOS	PFT	
PAHs	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	
	1-methyl naphthalene	1MNa
	2-methyl naphthalene	2MNa

	naphthalene	NAP
	acenaphthylene	ANY
	acenaphthene	ANA
	fluorene	FLU
	phenanthrene	PHE
	anthracene	ANT
	fluoranthene	FLT
	pyrene	PYR
	benzo[<i>a</i>]anthracene	BaA
	chrysene	CHR
	benzo[<i>b</i>]fluoranthene	BbF
	benzo[<i>k</i>]fluoranthene	BkF
	benzo[<i>a</i>]pyrene	BaP
	benzo[<i>e</i>]pyrene	BeP
	benzo[<i>j</i>]fluoranthene	BjF
	indeno[1,2,3- <i>cd</i>]pyrene	IPY
	dibenz[<i>a,h</i>]anthracene	DBA
	benzo[<i>ghi</i>]perylene	BPE
	Perylene	PER
	Triphenylene	TRF
	4- <i>H</i> -cyclopenta[<i>def</i>]PHE	CPHE
	retene	RET
	cyclopenta[<i>cd</i>]PYR	CPYR
	coronene	COR
	NAP, ANY, ANA, FLU, PHE, ANT, FLT, PYR, BaA, CHR, BbF, BkF, BaP, IPY, DBA, BPE	ΣPAH16
	Sum of BaP, BaA, CHR, BbF, BkF, DBA, IPY, BPE of the European Food Safety Authority	PAH EFSA 8
Pharmaceuticals and biocides		
Pharm/hormones	17β-Estradiol	E2
Pharm/hormones	17α-ethynylestradiol	EE2
Pharm/β-blocker	Atenolol	ATE
Pharm/β-blocker	Metoprolol	MET
Pharm/β-blocker	Sotalol	SOT
Pharm/pain killer	Paracetamol	PCM
Pharm/pain killer	Diclofenac	DCF
Pharm/pain killer	Ibuprofene	IBU
Pharm/against epilepsy	carbamazepine	CBZ
Biozid	Triclosan	TCS
Biozid	Triclocarban	TCC
Pharm/ against epilepsy	Sulphadiazine	SDZ
Pharm/antibiotics	Tetracycline	TET
Pharm/antibiotics	Norfloxacin	NOF
Pharm/antibiotics	Ciprofloxacin	CIF
Pharm/antibiotics	Ofloxacin	OF
Pharm/antibiotics	Doxycycline	
Pharm/hormons	Estradiol	
Pharm/hormons	Estrone	

PBDEs	Polybrominated diphenyl ethers	
Flame retardants	2,4,4'-tribromodiphenyl ether	PBDE-28
	2,2',4,4'-tetrabromodiphenyl ether	PBDE-47
	2,3',4,4'-tetrabromodiphenyl ether	PBDE-66
	2,2',3,4,4'-pentabromodiphenyl ether	PBDE-85
	2,2',4,4',5-pentabromodiphenyl ether	PBDE-99
	2,2',4,4',6-pentabromodiphenyl ether	PBDE-100
	2,2',4,4',5,5'-hexabromodiphenyl ether	PBDE-153
	2,2',4,4',5,6'-hexabromodiphenyl ether	PBDE-154
	2,2',3,4,4',5',6-heptabromodiphenyl ether	PBDE-183
	decabromodiphenyl ether	PBDE-209
	Hexabromocyclododecane	HBCD
	Tetrabromobisphenol A	TBBPA
Phthalates		
Softener	Di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate	DEHP
	benzyl butyl phthalate	BBP
	Dibutyl phthalate	DBP
	Diisobutyl phthalate	DIBP
Phenoles		
Alkylphenol	4-Nonylphenol	NP
Alkylphenol	4-Octaphenol	OP
Bisphenol	Bisphenol A	BPA
Alkylphenol	nonylphenol monoethoxylate	NP1EO
Alkylphenol	nonylphenol diethoxylate	NP2EO
Aromatic hydrocarbons		
	Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene and Xylenes	Σ BTEX
	Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene, Xylenes, and styrene	BTEXS
PCBs	Polychlorinated biphenyls	
	Congeners 28, 52, 101, 138, 153, 180	Σ PCB6
	Congeners 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153, 180	Σ PCB7
Aliphatic hydrocarbons		
	aliphatic hydrocarbons + mineral oil	C9-C40
	sum of hydrocarbons (C10-C40 or C10-12, C13-16, C17-21, C22-C40)	Σ HC
Parabens		
	Methylparaben	MeP
	ethylparaben	EtP
	isopropylparaben	iPrP
	propylparaben	PrP
	isobutylparaben	iBuP
	butylparaben	BuP
	benzylparaben	BzP
Alkylbenzene sulfonates		
	linear alkylbenzene sulphonates	LAS-C10
	linear alkylbenzene sulphonates	LAS-C11

	linear alkylbenzene sulphonates	LAS-C12
	linear alkylbenzene sulphonates	LAS-C13
PCDD/F	Polychlorinated dibenzodioxins/-furans	
	sum of all tetrachlorodibenzofurans	Total TCDF
	sum of all pentachlorodibenzofurans	Total PeCDF
	sum of all hexachlorodibenzofurans	Total HxCDF
	sum of all heptachlorodibenzofurans	Total HpCDF
	octachlorodibenzofurans	OCDF
	octachlorodibenzodioxins	OCDD
	sum of all tetrachlorodibenzodioxins	Total TCDD
	sum of all pentachlorodibenzodioxins	Total PeCDD
	sum of all hexachlorodibenzodioxins	Total HxCDD
	sum of all heptachlorodibenzodioxins	Total HpCDD
	International Toxic Equivalent	I-TEQ
	sum of all polychlorinated dibenzodioxins	total PCDDs
	sum of all polychlorinated dibenzofurans	total PCDFs
	dioxinlike PCB	DL-PCB
Sulfonamides		
	perfluoroktansulfonamide	FOSA
	fluortelomersulfonate	6:2FTS
	fluortelomersulfonate	8:2FTS
	perfluortridekane acid	PFTTrDA
	perfluortetradekane acid	PFTeDA
	N-methylperfluoroktansulfonamide	MeFOSA
	N-ethylperfluoroktansulfonamide	EtFOSA
	N-methylperfluoroktansulfonamidetanole	MeFOSE
	N-ethylperfluoroktansulfonamidetanole	EtFOSE
Paraffins		
	C ₁₄ -C ₁₇ , medium chain chlorinated paraffins	MCCP
	C ₁₀ -C ₁₃ , short chain chlorinated paraffins	SCCP
OCP	Organochlorine pesticides	
	hexachlorobenzene	HCB
	γ-hexachlorocyclohexane	γ-HCH
	4,4 Dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene	4,4 DDE
	2,4 Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane	2,4 DDT
	2,4 Dichlorodiphenyldichloroethane	2,4 DDD
Halogens		
	Adsorbable, organically bound halogens	AOX
	Extractable organic halides	EOX
Biuret		
	C ₂ H ₅ N ₃ O ₂	

Table A 3: Four categories could be classified of all **regulated** contaminants: organic compounds, metals, impurities, and pathogens. Abbreviations are explained in Table A 1 and Table A 2. (Please note that the author categorized the contaminants and the table has therefore no official character.)

Organic contaminants	Metals	Impurities	Pathogens
Antibiotics	¹³⁷ Cs	Cl	Campylobacter species
AOX	Al	Contaminating plant seeds	Clostridium
BaP	As	Glass, metal, (micro)plastics	E. coli
BbF	Cd	Impurities	E. coli O157:H7 (EHEC)
PBDE-209	Co	Inert lithoid >5 mm	Enterococcus
BeP + BjF	Cr	Radioactivity	Helminth eggs
BTEX	CrVI	Stones	Helminth eggs + larvae
C ₂ H ₅ N ₃ O ₂	Cs	Weed seeds	Listeria monocytogenes
EOX	Cu		Root rot fungus
FLT	Hg		Salmonella
FLT + PHE + PYR	Ni		
Hydrocarbon indices	Pb		
Mineral oil hydrocarbons	Se		
Organochlorine pesticides	Tl		
PAHs 6 borneff ^a	V		
PAH EFSA 8	Zn		
PCB6			
PCDD/F			
PFOS			
PFT			
∑PAH16			
∑PCB6			

^a: neither PAH compounds nor borneff specified

Table A 4: Four categories could be classified of all **monitored** contaminants: organic compounds, metals, impurities, and pathogens. Abbreviations are explained in Table A 1 and Table A 2. (Please note that the author categorized the contaminants and the table has therefore no official character.)

Organic contaminants	Metals	Impurities	Pathogens
All compounds listed in Table A 2 except biuret (carbamylurea)	Ag	Cl	Cestodes
	Al	Impurities	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>
	As	Inerts <3.33 mm, >10 mm	<i>E. coli</i>
	B	Inerts >10 mm	Fecal coliform
	Ba	Inerts >3.33 mm <10 mm	Enterococcus
	Bi	Microplastics	Enterobacteriae
	Cd	Plastics <3.33 mm	Helminth eggs
	Co	Plastics >10 mm	Helminth eggs + larvae
	Cr	Plastics >3.33 <10 mm	Nematodes
	Cr III	Stones	Salmonella
	Cr VI		<i>Streptococchi faecalis</i>
	Cu		<i>Teania saginata</i>
	Hg		<i>Teania solium</i>
	Li		Trematodes
	Mn		
	Mo		
	Ni		
	Pb		
	Sb		
	Se		
Sn			
Sr			
Tl			
U			
V			
Y			
Zn			

^a: neither PAH compounds nor borneff specified